

Prophylactic and Therapeutic Potential Effects of Melatonin Pretreated Bone Marrow Mesenchymal Stem Cells against Cisplatin-Induced Cardiac Toxicity in Albino Rats

Ahmed Elzainy

Cairo University, Department of Anatomy, Cairo, Egypt
Qassim University, Department of Anatomy and Histology, Qassim, Saudi Arabia

Email: abirelsadik63@gmail.com

Abstract:

Introduction: Cisplatin, one of the most effective chemotherapeutic agent, is proved to have toxic effects on many body organs especially the heart. Bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BM-MSCs) and melatonin were investigated to treat myocardial toxicity separately. However, their concomitant potential effect was not properly investigated.

Aim of the work: The present study was conducted to evaluate the potential prophylactic and therapeutic effects of BM-MSCs pretreated with melatonin against cisplatin myocardial toxicity.

Material and Methods: Twenty adult male albino rats were divided into four groups; group I (control group), did not receive any drugs, group II (given 10 mg/kg body weight Cisplatin in a single dose) and group III and IV (given the same dose of cisplatin and one systemic injection of melatonin pretreated BM-MSCs (1×10^6) diluted in 0.5 ml of PBS at day one (group III) as a prophylactic treatment and at day 14 (group IV) as a therapeutic dose. Blood samples were analyzed for serum cardiac marker enzymes; CK-MB and Troponin. Samples from the left ventricle were taken and prepared for fluorescent study, gene expression for TNF- α , IL-1 β and NF- κ B levels, light microscopic examination, α -SMA and Bax immunohistochemical study and histomorphometric analysis. Results: The present study confirmed the cardiotoxic effect of cisplatin, manifested by significant increase in serum CK-MB and Troponin and in the expression of pro-inflammatory factors; TNF- α , IL-1 β and NF- κ B levels. Degeneration of myocardial cells and nuclear pyknosis with congested blood vessels and blood extravasation were detected. Significant decrease in α SMA and increase in Bax immunoreaction were revealed. Melatonin pretreated BM-MSCs were shown to protect and regenerate the cardiomyocytes. Prophylactic treated group showed significantly better effects than therapeutic group.

Conclusion: The present study confirmed that prophylactic treatment is more efficient than therapeutic treatment of melatonin pretreated BM-MSCs against the cardiac toxicity of cisplatin. So, it is recommended to supply the treatment from the start in concomitant with chemotherapy.

Keywords:

Cardiomyocytes, Cisplatin, Melatonin, BM-MSCs, PCR.

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Protective Role of N-Acetylcysteine on Isoprenaline-Induced Myocardial Injury: Histological, Immunohistochemical and Morphometric Study

S. Zaki¹, I. Abdalla², A. El Sadik³, E. Mohamed⁴, S. Kaooh⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Cairo University, Department of Anatomy, Cairo, Egypt

³Qassim University, Department of Anatomy and Histology, Qassim, Saudi Arabia

Email: abeer.ouaida@kasralainy.edu.eg

Abstract:

Several researchers studied the protective effect of the N-acetylcysteine (NAC) when it was given before the induction of myocardial infarction (MI). Other researchers studied such protective effect when it was before and after the MI. The missing data are the comparison between the protective effect of NAC before myocardial injury with its protective effect both before and after myocardial injury. The aim of the study was to compare the cardioprotective effect of NAC on the isoprenaline-induced myocardial injury before the isoprenaline (ISP) injection with its protective effect both before and after the ISP injection. This study was applied over both short and long time periods. A total of 90 male adult Wistar albino rats were used in the study. The rats were divided into four groups: control group, ISP-treated group, NAC-pretreated group and NAC-pre- & post-treated group. Based on the duration of the experiment, the second and third groups were further subdivided into a and b groups. Histological, immunohistochemical and histomorphometric analysis were used. The myocytes in the ISP-treated groups were fragmented, disrupted with karyolysis. The blood vessels were dilated, congested and associated with blood extravasation, interstitial edema and cellular inflammatory infiltration. Much improvement was observed in the NAC pre-treated group. Focal degeneration was detected in the muscle fibers. The capillaries were normal. Minimal blood extravasation and cellular infiltration were seen. The cardiac muscle fibers in the NAC-pre- & posttreated group were regularly arranged. The mean collagen fiber area percent of the ISP-treated groups was significantly higher by 8.3-folds and 10.1-folds as compared with that of the control group and was also higher by 5.5-folds and 6.8-folds as compared with that of the NACpre- & posttreated groups. The α -SMA area percent in the ISP-treated groups was significantly higher by 12.2-folds and 23.9-folds as compared with that of the control group and was higher by 7.5-folds and 15-folds as compared with that of the NAC-pre- & posttreated groups. The mean PCNA area percent of the ISP-treated groups was significantly higher by 126.2 and 164.8% as compared with that of the control group and was higher by 106.3 and 141.5% as compared with that of NAC-pre- & posttreated groups. ISP had deleterious effects on the heart. Administration of NAC before ISP injection could largely reduce the ISP-induced short- and long-term alterations. The protection was maximum with the use of NAC before the ISP injection and continued after the injection for 12 days.

Keywords:

N acetyl cysteine, Myocardial injury, ISP.

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The Reuse of (Single-Use) Cardiac Disposable of Coronary Angiography and Angioplasty: Safety and Economic Issues in Gaza Strip

Mohammed Habib¹, Ahmad Musran² and Mohammad Al Agha³

¹ Department of Consultant Cardiologist, Gaza

² Department of Head nurse of Cardiac Catheterization Unit, Gaza

³ Department of Environmental Sciences, Gaza

Abstract:

Background: Most countries outside the United States routinely reuse disposable medical equipment. We investigated the reuse of puncture needle, wires, sheath, manifold, inflation device, diagnostic and angioplasty catheters restored by a process strictly controlled for bioburden and sterility, in patients undergoing diagnostic coronary angiography and PCI.

Methods: We enrolled total 135 samples from different disposable (18 catheters, 6 manifold, 6 pressure line, 6 coronary wire, 6 femoral sheath, 2 inflation devices, 1 puncture needle) from 3 hospital in Gaza strip (45 sample from each hospital), were shipped to a central facility and were decontaminated, cleaned and tested for sterilization. The disposables were sterilized by exposure to Formaldehyde (90 samples,) or Cidex (45 samples) using a carefully validated protocol. Safety point: After sterilization disposables well rinsing with normal saline then taking swaps from outer side and inner side and were collected into a suitable container and transferred directly from collecting site to the laboratory to make culture. Cost-effective point: An average of five uses for diagnostic and three uses for angioplasty disposables.

Results: The disposable materials were collected from Aid Hospital and the European Gaza Hospital and sterilized by exposure to formaldehyde were negative results. while samples was collected from Al Shifa hospitals and sterilized by Cidex were 3 staphylococcus positive results. The procedure success rates similar to those of new products. Cost analysis suggests that An average of five uses for diagnostic disposables and three uses for angioplasty disposables may save approximately \$5000 and \$11500 respectively, per 100 procedures

Conclusion: Reuse of medical devices labelled “single use only” is common in Palestinian hospitals. Restoration of disposable of coronary angiography and angioplasty using a controlled process appears to be safe, cost saving in sterilization by Formaldehyde (but not Cidex) with success rates similar to those of new products and no detectable sacrifice in performance.

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Comparison of Cardiovascular Autonomic Control in Patients who Underwent Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting or Correction of Acquired Valvular Heart Disease

A.R. Kiselev,^{1,2,*} V.A. Shvartz,¹ A.S. Karavaev^{2,3} E.I. Borovkova,^{2,3} O.M. Posnenkova,²
O.L. Bockeria¹

¹ Bakoulev Scientific Center for Cardiovascular Surgery, Russia

² Saratov State Medical University, Institute of Cardiological Research, Russia

³ Saratov State University, Department of Dynamic Modeling and Biomedical Engineering, Russia

Abstract:

Aim was to study the cardiovascular auto-nomic control in patients who underwent coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) or correction of acquired valvular heart disease (CAVHD).

Material and Methods — In this study we included 42 patients (12 women; 62±9 years), who underwent CABG, and 36 patients (16 women; 54±15 years) who underwent CAVHD. The synchronous 15 minutes records of electrocardiogram and photoplethysmogram were performed in all patients before and in after surgery. Time domain and frequency domain measures of heart rate variability (HRV) and index of synchronization between low-frequency oscillations in HRV and photoplethysmogram (index S) were analyzed.

Results — Most studied autonomic indices did not have statistically significant differences between patients with CABG and CAVHD in the study stages, except for heart rate, which was higher in patients before CAVHD (Table).

Conclusion — The values of HRV and index S do not depend on the difference in the clinical status and the features of performed cardiac surgical interventions between patients with CABG and CAVHD.

Keywords:

Cardiovascular autonomic control, coronary artery bypass grafting, valvular heart disease, heart rate variability.

Table. Parameters of the cardiovascular auto-nomic control in studied groups

Parameters	CABG (n=42)	CAVHD ПИС (n=36)
Before surgery		
Index S, %	24.7 (18.3, 35.2)	22.5 (13.4, 27.4)
HR, min-1	67 (60, 72)	69 (65, 80)*
SDNN, ms	34.9 (24.9, 52.3)	37.7 (28.4, 53.1)
TP, ms ²	493 (311, 1247)	425 (246, 969)
LF%	24.4 (16.5, 34.6)	29.4 (17.1, 36.9)
HF%	21.6 (9.5, 47.0)	20.2 (11.1, 29.7)
LF/HF	1.2 (0.6, 2.7)	1.4 (0.6, 2.9)
5-7 days after surgery		
Index S, %	20.3 (10.2, 27.5)	20.2 (15.5, 28.1)
HR, min-1	78 (73, 87)	74 (66, 90)
SDNN, ms	15.6 (11.3, 41.0)	18.0 (11.1, 71.9)
TP, ms ²	84 (26, 496)	125 (36, 2735)
LF%	26.6 (18.1, 36.4)	30.8 (21.8, 39.8)
HF%	26.3 (10.8, 46.4)	23.7 (9.7, 43.4)
LF/HF	0.8 (0.5, 3.4)	1.2 (0.6, 2.9)

Data presented as median with low and upper quartiles – Me (LQ, UQ). * statistically significant difference (P<0.05, Mann–Whitney test) from the similar indexes in patients who underwent CABG.

HR, heart rate; SDNN, standard deviations of normal to normal intervals; TP, total power of HRV spectrum; HF%, percentages of high-frequency range in total power of photoplethysmogram spectrum; LF%, percentages of low-frequency range in total power of photoplethysmogram spectrum.

Interaction of Baroreflex Regulation of Heart Rhythm and Peripheral Blood Filling in Healthy Newborns

A.R. Kiselev,^{1,2,*} Yu.V. Popova,¹ E.N. Mureeva,¹ V.V. Skazkina,² E.I. Borovkova,^{1,2}
O.S. Pani-na,¹ A.S. Karavaev,^{1,3} V.I. Gridnev,¹ Yu.V. Chernenkov¹

¹ Saratov State Medical University, Institute of Cardiological Research, Russia

² Saratov State University, Department of Dynamic Modeling and Biomedical Engineering, Russia

³ Saratov Branch of the Institute of Radio Engineering and Electronics of Russian Academy of Sciences, Laboratory of Nonlinear Dynamics Modelling

Abstract:

Introduction: The purpose of this pilot re-search was a comparative study of the spectral power density in the low-frequency (LF) band of heart rate variability (HRV) and synchronization of LF oscillations characterizing baroreflex in the cardiovascular autonomic control in healthy newborns and adults.

Material and Methods: The study included 15 healthy newborns and 60 healthy adults (18-34 years old). We performed synchronous recording of electrocardiograms and photoplethysmograms (PPG) at rest (duration 10 minutes). The spectral power density in the LF band (0.04-0.15 Hz) of HRV and the index of synchronization of low-frequency oscillations in HRV and PPG (index S) were estimated. Data presented as median with lower and upper quartiles – Me (LQ, UQ). We used the Mann–Whitney test to compare the variables between the groups.

Results: In newborns, the peak of LF oscillations was predominantly in the range 0.07–0.09 Hz. Newborns had lower LF% values than adults: 22.8 (14.1, 29.4) vs 32.9 (25.1, 41.9) (P=0.009). The S index in newborns was 20.1 (16.9, 26.5)%, and 33.2 (21.2, 45.4)% in healthy adults (P=0.023).

Conclusion : We have first shown that the interaction of baroreflex regulation of heart rhythm and peripheral blood filling in healthy newborns is characterized by lower values of index S than in healthy adults. It can be explained by the immaturity of the autonomic regulatory elements of cardiovascular system.

Keywords:

Cardiovascular autonomic control, baroreflex, newborns.

Identification of the genetic etiology of malignant arrhythmia in hypertrophic cardiomyopathy

Dao Wu Wang

State Key Laboratory of Reproductive Medicine, The Centre for Clinical Reproductive Medicine, and Division of Cardiology, the First Affiliated Hospital of Nanjing Medical University, China.

Abstract:

Background: Malignant cardiac arrhythmia, a common cause of death in patients with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM), is usually thought to be a natural outcome of HCM. The mechanisms underlying arrhythmias in HCM are not well understood and the effective risk stratifications in HCM patients are not yet defined. Genetic causes other than HCM-related sarcomere variants may underlie arrhythmias in HCM patients. Hence, the aim of the study was to identify the concomitant genetic etiology of arrhythmias in HCM patients.

Methods: We combined whole-exome sequencing (WES) and massively parallel targeted next-generation sequencing (predefined panel) to screen seven special HCM pedigrees with arrhythmias and two separate cohorts containing a total of 1222 unrelated sporadic HCM patients (647 in the discovery cohort and 575 in the replication cohort) who were recruited from three medical centers: 583 patients (315 in the discovery cohort and 268 in the replication cohort) with arrhythmias (HCM-A group) and 639 patients (332 in the discovery cohort and 307 in the replication cohort) without arrhythmias (HCM-NA group). All identified causative variants were directly Sanger sequenced and screened in 700 unrelated matched healthy controls without HCM or arrhythmias.

Results: We identified arrhythmia-related pathogenic or likely pathogenic variants in 6.69% (39/583) of patients in the sporadic HCM-A group (6.67% in the discovery cohort and 6.72% in the replication cohort) but only 0.31% (2/639) of patients in the HCM-NA group ($P=6.30 \times 10^{-10}$). Among all patients with arrhythmia-related variants, our results revealed the following arrhythmia syndromes: long QT syndrome, atrial fibrillation, ventricular tachycardia, Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome, atrioventricular block, sick sinus syndrome, Brugada syndrome, and catecholaminergic polymorphic ventricular tachycardia. Of note, WES missed 6.45% (2/31) of the pathogenic variants identified by targeted sequencing using a predefined panel.

Conclusion: Our study results from the discovery cohort support our hypothesis that genes associated with arrhythmias underlie the arrhythmia syndromes in HCM-A patients, and subsequently, results from our replication cohort successfully validated and confirmed those findings. Thus, in HCM families with arrhythmias, genetic screening should not be limited to the sarcomeric variants that lead to HCM.

Keywords:

Arrhythmia, Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, Next-generation sequencing, Whole-exome sequencing, Genetic diagnosis

Inhibition of BRD4 attenuates transverse aortic constriction- and TGF- β -induced endothelial-mesenchymal transition and cardiac fibrosis.

Shuai Song

Xinhua Hospital, School of Medicine, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai, China.

Abstract:

Cardiac fibrosis (CF), a process characterized by potentiated proliferation of cardiac fibroblasts and excessive secretion and deposition of extracellular matrix (ECM) from the cells, contributes strongly to the pathogenesis of a series of cardiovascular (CV) diseases, including AMI, heart failure and atrial fibrillation. Endothelial-mesenchymal transition (EndMT), one of the sources of transformed cardiac fibroblasts, has been reported as a key factor involved in CF. However, the molecular basis of EndMT has not been thoroughly elucidated to date. At the posttranscriptional level, of the three epigenetic regulators, writer and eraser are reported to be involved in EndMT, but the role of reader in the process is still unknown. In this study, we aimed to explore the role of Bromodomain-containing protein 4 (BRD4), an acetyl-lysine reader protein, in EndMT-induced CF and related mechanisms. We found that BRD4 was upregulated in endothelial cells (ECs) in the pressure-overload mouse heart and that its functional inhibitor JQ1 potently attenuated the TAC-induced CF and preserved cardiac function. In umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) and mouse aortic endothelial cells (MAECs), both JQ1 and shRNA-mediated silencing of BRD4 blocked TGF- β -induced EC migration, EndMT and ECM synthesis and preserved the EC sprouting behavior, possibly through the downregulation of a group of transcription factors specific for EndMT (Snail, Twist and Slug), the Smads pathway and TGF- β receptor I. In the absence of TGF- β stimulation, ectopic expression of BRD4 alone could facilitate EndMT, accelerate migration and increase the synthesis of ECM. In vivo, JQ1 also attenuated TAC-induced EndMT and CF, which was consistent with JQ1's intracellular mechanisms of action. Our results showed that BRD4 plays a critical role in EndMT-induced CF and that targeting BRD4 might be a novel therapeutic option for CF.

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Yunling Gao

¹ Saratov State Medical University, Institute of Cardiological Research, Department of Innovative Cardiological Information Technology, Russia

² Regional Clinical Hospital, Saratov, Russia

Abstract:

The National Institutes of Health (NIH) is the primary medical research and funding agency of the United States government. Its mission is to seek fundamental knowledge about the nature and behavior of living systems and the application of that knowledge to enhance health, lengthen life, and reduce the burdens of illness and disability. NIH invests more than \$30 billion (2019, 80%) of its funds on extramural research (outside the NIH), being the largest source of funding for biomedical research in the world. NIH is made up of 27 Institutes and Centers, each with a specific research agenda often focusing on particular diseases or body systems. The National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (NHLBI) awards a wide range of basic, translational, and clinical cardiovascular researches to understand its fundamental mechanisms and to seek new therapeutic interventions for cardiovascular diseases. Over the decades, the NHLBI-funded cardiovascular research has contributed to better understanding of mechanisms at the molecular, genetic and cellular levels, and improved diagnosis and treatment for cardiovascular diseases.

This presentation is to visit the breadth and depth of the NHLBI-funded cardiovascular research, highlight main achievements, and identify challenges and opportunities, which may stimulate innovative research in treating cardiovascular diseases. As the cardiovascular field moves forward, a deliberate, more integrated basic and clinical research effort is needed to address gaps in our understanding and develop clinical therapeutics.

Biography:

Yunling Gao, M.D., Ph.D., is a Program Director at the Vascular Biology and Hypertension Branch, Division of Cardiovascular Sciences (DCVS) of the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (NHLBI), National Institutes of Health (NIH) of the United States. Dr. Gao was trained as a physician in China and a biomedical research scientist in the United States. She obtained her Ph.D. at the University of Cincinnati College of Medicine in 1993 and completed her postdoctoral training at the Harvard Medical School and Brigham and Women's Hospital. In 1997, she joined Albert Einstein College of Medicine as a faculty and Instructor of Medicine. In 2002, she joined Eli Lilly and Company for pharmaceutical drug discover for the treatment of ischemic cardiovascular disease, dyslipidemia, and atherosclerosis, and later on drug development and commercialization while she served as a clinical research scientist in cardiovascular clinical trials and global patient safety. Dr. Gao has been working at the NIH since 2008 as a Program Director. She currently manages a large research grant portfolio in vascular and endothelial biology, angiogenesis and vascular remodeling, and their related cardiovascular diseases. She has involved in overseeing multiple contracts for global health clinical studies and regulatory affairs in Bangladesh, China, India, Peru, and South Africa for reducing chronic non-communicable diseases.

Impact of Diabetes Mellitus on Myocardial Reperfusion and Left Ventricular Remodelling In Patients with Acute Myocardial Infarction Treated with Primary Coronary Intervention

Khaled Emad El din Elrabat , Eman Saeed Elkeshk, Mohamed Helmy Elsayed ,
Shereen Ibrahim Farag d, Mohamed Mousa Okdae

Professor of cardiology, Benha University, Egypt.
Assistant Professor of Cardiology, Benha University, Egypt.
Consultant of cardiology, The National Heart Institute, Egypt
Lecturer of Cardiology, Benha University, Egypt.
Resident of cardiology, The National Heart Institute, Egypt.

Abstract:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) in patients after acute myocardial infarction (MI) has been shown to be a strong predictor of short-and long-term mortality. It has also been recognized that DM is associated with an increased rate of post-infarction heart failure.

Aim of the study: To evaluate the impact of diabetes mellitus on myocardial reperfusion after primary PCI in patients with acute myocardial infarction utilizing, resolution of ST- segment elevation and myocardial blush grade (MBG) and To evaluate the impact of diabetes mellitus on left ventricular remodelling using 2-D speckle tracking.

Methods: The study population consisted of 100 patients with anterior STEMI (50 diabetic and 50 non diabetic) all patients underwent 1ry PCI. Conventional 2D echocardiography to assess LVEF, EDV and ESV and speckle tracking echocardiography to assess LV global longitudinal strain and global circumferential strain was done within 72hr of admission and after 3 months later and patients with LV remodeling, i.e. an increase >20% in LV end-diastolic volume (LVEDV), were identified.

Results: No significant difference was found regarding baseline clinical, angiographic and echocardiographic characteristics except in MBG3 (18% vs. 54% $p = 0.001$), MBG1 (32% vs. 8% $p = 0.003$), complete ST segment resolution (18% vs. 48% $p = 0.001$) and Absent ST segment resolution (28% vs. 10% $p = 0.022$) between diabetics and non diabetics respectively. Despite a similar incidence of LV remodelling in DM and non DM groups (22% vs. 16%, $p = 0.444$), The 19 patients with LV remodelling had significantly more impaired LVEDV (99.84 ± 19.24 vs. 125.11 ± 19.96 , $p = 0.001$), and LV global longitudinal strain (GLS) ($-11.47 \pm 1.34\%$ vs. $-10.61 \pm 2.15\%$, $p = 0.021$). Change in end diastolic volume showed the strongest correlation with the GLS ($P = 0.042$, $r = 0.473$) and apical circumferential strain ($P = 0.028$, $r = 0.014$). Furthermore, apical circumferential strain demonstrated the highest diagnostic accuracy: area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, with sensitivity 84.2% and specificity 88.9%, using a cutoff value >-11.7% and GLS with sensitivity 89.5% and specificity 65.4%, using a cutoff value >-12.5% for prediction of LV remodelling.

Conclusion: Despite worse microvascular reperfusion and ST segment resolution in STEMI patients with diabetes, the incidence of LV remodelling was similar compared to non-DM patients and LV apical CS and GLS is a predictive parameter of future adverse remodelling.

Biography:

Mohamed Mousa Okda is a Cardiologist working at National Heart Institute in Egypt. His main interest include Interventional Cardiology. Also, he is a member of Egyptian Society of Cardiology.